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of **EXPRESSION**
A Creative Folio

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Safest Refuge

Those times when you feel
Like the whole earth is crashing down on you,
The ground feels unsure beneath your feet,
And even breathing hurts.

You just want to run.
Run from the sadness,
Run from the noise,
Run from yourself,
And shut the world away.

That's when you realize,
There's nowhere left to go.
No shelter, no place to hide,
But in Sujood.

Where the forehead meets the earth,
And the soul finds its sanctuary.
The safest refuge,
The gentlest comfort,
The strongest protector,
The most generous provider
Allah (SWT).

In that sacred stillness,
Where tears fall unseen,
You are heard.
You are held.
You are healed.